

METHODS OF USING TOOTHPASTE

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Abstract: From an early age, teeth need daily hygiene. In this article, we will talk about the role that toothpaste plays in oral hygiene. Let's find out what it consists of, what types of toothpastes there are and how to choose it correctly.

Key words: Toothpaste, Professional pastes, purpose.

Toothpaste is a complex multicomponent substance, the purpose of which is:
cleansing;

deodorization;

oral antiseptics;

strengthening the surface of the teeth.

The earliest mention of the first prototype of pasta dates back to the 4th century AD, and it consisted of salt, pepper, mint and iris.

Some patients ask themselves: why do you need toothpaste, because one brush is enough? However, a simple mechanical cleaning will help to cope with plaque, but it is not enough to neutralize pathogenic bacteria and saturate the enamel with useful substances.

Unfortunately, it is impossible to protect your teeth around the clock without special tools. Such products include toothpaste. Thanks to it, there is a complex effect on the oral cavity, and not only the mechanical removal of plaque.

If you do not use toothpaste regularly, the process of enamel demineralization begins. In this case, teeth lose useful minerals, including calcium and fluoride. Under the action of organic acids, this process is accelerated at times.

Therefore, toothpaste is an indispensable assistant in daily oral hygiene.

How to use toothpaste correctly?

Toothpaste should be used twice a day. In the morning, plaque and germs accumulated in the mouth during sleep are removed. In the evening, everything that has accumulated during the day is cleaned out. It is not recommended to use toothpaste more often, as this negatively affects the enamel of the teeth.

Before brushing your teeth, be sure to rinse your mouth with warm boiled water, and then squeeze a small amount of paste onto your toothbrush. The cleaning process should take about 2-3 minutes. The brush should move downward, sweeping out all the "garbage" from under the gums. After cleaning, rinse your mouth thoroughly so that the paste pieces do not remain in your mouth.

Available oral care products

A toothbrush is the most common oral care option.

This remedy is necessary to eliminate plaque on the teeth and remove pieces of food that get stuck in the interdental spaces.

Interdental brushes are special brushes for deeper cleaning of the gaps between the teeth, which cope with this task better than conventional brushes.

Using a toothpaste with a good composition is important for maintaining oral health. A mouthwash is also an excellent hygiene product. Both products help eliminate bacteria and food residues, prevent caries, plaque and other problems with teeth and gums.

Professional pastes. Specialized preparations with a high content of abrasive particles fall into this group. In everyday life, such pastes are practically not used, but are used by dentists during professional dental cleaning procedures.

In separate groups, you can select:

Phosphate-containing pastes, which are considered more effective and better than fluorinated ones, since they are used at any age.

Anti-caries pastes prescribed to strengthen enamel and prevent the inflammatory process in the gums. Special pastes, which include bleaching and pastes for smokers. Separate formulations are provided for smokers. In addition to bleaching components, silver nitrates are added to the pastes, which suppress cravings for a bad habit. Toothpastes for young children are more stringent in terms of requirements, as they should not contain harmful substances and have a more pleasant taste with aroma.

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